

Studying Vipaka from Ayurveda as A Clue to Modern Pharmacological Research

Shounak Nazar¹, Mehndi Sharma², Archana Belge³

¹ Research Scholar, Pacific University, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India, Faculty, Symbiosis Institute of Business Management Nagpur

² PhD Guide, Assistant Professor, Pacific Institute of Hotel Management, Pacific University, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

³ PhD Guide, Professor & HOD, Dept. of Swasthavritta & Yoga, Shri Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur, Maharashtra

ABSTRACT

Discovery of extraoral taste receptors and their role in digestion and metabolism has been the topic of discussion among the gastroenterologists and Pharmacologists in last two decades. Ayurveda has a concept of Post Digestive taste called as Vipaka and is fundamental to the fate of digestion and metabolism in human beings. Classical texts in Ayurveda, mention three kinds of Vipaka: Madhura (sweet), Amla (sour), and Katu (pungent). These influence the further processes metabolism. Modern research in Biochemistry, run on same lines by confirming the presence of taste receptors in gastrointestinal tract which act as sensors for the local processes of digestion, absorption, and excretion that happens in gut. The concept can be utilized best by the pharmacologists in influencing nutrient drug interaction thereby positively influencing the drug absorption. Current study is the review of 27 research papers (from 2001 to 2025) the findings of which demonstrates the similarity between concept of Vipaka and the activity of gut receptors. This study is a qualitative correlational synthesis generating a hypothesis for further Pharmacological Research in this area.

Keywords: Vipaka, Ayurveda, Extraoral Taste Receptors, Post-digestive Effect, Nutrigenomics, Gut-Brain Axis, Gut Signalling.

INTRODUCTION

Taste of food is the primary screening method used by human body that signaling the brain and orienting the digestive system for incoming food. The food after entering the stomach gets digested and absorbed into the blood stream. This absorption takes place with concentration gradient dependent system and a calory dependent sodium potassium channel. The signal that makes these systems operational was under focus from long time. In India, an ancient system of medicine called Ayurveda, that originated over 5,000 years ago, provides a time-tested dietary approach that emphasizes balance in food and individual constitution. Unlike modern nutrition science, which primarily focuses on calorie intake and macronutrient composition, Ayurveda considers food as a means of maintaining harmony between mind, body, and spirit.

Ayurveda classifies food based on its intrinsic qualities, post-digestive effects, and its impact on an individual's body constitution (Prakriti). Ayurveda mentions the role of three kinds of fundamental energies called Kapha, Pitta and Vata together called as Dosha. The principles of Ayurveda suggest that food should be selected and prepared according to one's dominant dosha, seasonal variations (Rutucharya), and digestive capacity (Agni). The important Ayurvedic dietary concepts include taste (Rasa), functional quality of food (Guna), potency (Virya), post digestive taste (Vipaka) and therapeutic effect (Karma). There are few more concepts like dietary rules and regulations known as Ahara Vidhi, and compatibility of ingredients expressed under the concepts of pathya, apathya and viruddha ahara and the diet as per seasonal variations known as rutucharya. These principles ensure that food not only

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supplies nutrition to the body but also supports digestion and prevents the accumulation of toxins (Ama). Despite its holistic approach to nutrition, Ayurveda lacks approval of modern science keeping available solutions in accessible to service of mankind. The concepts of Ayurveda seem to be misunderstood than rightly tested.

Current advances in molecular biology over the last two decades reveal that the fundamental philosophy behind the concepts of Ayurveda is not different from current logical thinking patterns of modern scientists. As per modern research the presence of the taste receptors is present in the oral cavity, as well as widely spread throughout the alimentary canal and other extra-oral tissues. These are known in general as G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs). These include the taste receptors called T1R family and the T2R family. These play major role in nutrient sensing, secretion of hormones, and regulating the pathways of metabolism. This highlights the system of chemosensory network in the gut that indicates the role of taste far beyond oral perception.

The convergence of Ayurvedic and modern perspectives offers a necessity of research in this area. Recent studies further underscore the influence of gut microbiota on receptor activation, suggesting that microbial metabolites may also contribute to the post-digestive outcomes envisioned in classical Ayurveda. Despite these parallels, systematic efforts to align Ayurvedic categories of Vipaka with receptor-mediated physiological mechanisms remain limited.

Understanding the basic concepts of Ayurveda Dietetics

Ayurveda, the ancient medical science of India, is rooted in a holistic understanding of health that integrates the body, psyche, and soul with nature and universe. The universe is created from the five fundamental elements (Pancha Mahabhutas): Akasha (ether), Vayu (air), Agni (fire), Jala (water), and Prithvi (earth). In an individual it operates through the balance of the three fundamental energies or Doshas called Vata, Pitta, and Kapha, where as in the qualities of other substances (Foods and Medicine) are studied under Dravya Guna Vignyana (Science of Substances) as Rasa Virya, Vipaka, Guna, Karma. Ideally Rasa is translated as Taste, Virya as Potency

of hot or cold kind, Vipaka as Post Digestive Taste, Guna as Functional Qualities, Therapeutic effect identified as Karma, and Prabhava as unpredictable effect. Here by taste we understand the various tastes of substances as Sweet, Salty, Sour, Pungent, Bitter and Astringent. There is a difference in recognizing the types of tastes sensed only with Astringent which is replaced by Umami Central to Ayurvedic pharmacology and dietetics is the concept of Rasa Panchaka, the fivefold classification of a substance's action on the body:

1. **Rasa** (initial taste)
2. **Guna** (physical properties)
3. **Virya** (potency—heating or cooling)
4. **Vipaka** (post-digestive taste/effect)
5. **Karma (Action of food on body)**

Among these, Vipaka holds particular significance. It represents the final transformation that a substance undergoes after digestion, primarily under the influence of digestive fire (Agni). While Rasa is experienced on the tongue and Virya reflects thermal action, Vipaka manifests its long-term impact on Doshas, Dhatus (tissues), and Malas (waste). Classical Ayurvedic texts consistently highlight that therapeutic efficacy often aligns more closely with Vipaka than with initial taste. When food is digested it goes through the transformation phase caked Vipaka where the all six tastes in foods are transformed into various post digestive tastes.

Although there are other theories on types of Vipaka named Shadvidha Vipaka Vada (six kinds of Vipaka), Panchavidha Vipaka Vada (five kinds of vipaka), Trividha Vipaka Vada (three kinds of Vipaka) and Dwividha Vipaka Vada (two kinds of Vipaka)

Vipaka is traditionally classified into three types (Trividha Vipaka Vada):

- **Madhura (Sweet):** Promotes Kapha, nourishes tissues, pacifies Vata and Pitta.
- **Amla (Sour):** Enhances Pitta and Kapha, stimulates digestion.

- **Katu (Pungent):** Increases Vata and Pitta, reduces Kapha, supports detoxification.

It literally means that the food with various six different tastes, after digestion is converted into the bolus with three basic tastes i.e. sweet sour and pungent.

Modern science is now validating the systemic role of taste through the discovery of taste receptors in extraoral tissues. These receptors influence digestion, nutrient absorption, metabolism, working of immune system, and functioning of endocrine system. This presents a reasonable opportunity of deeper study of the concept of Vipaka.

This study explores the possibility of establishing the relationship between the post-digestive taste (Vipaka) as described in Ayurveda with presence of extra-oral taste receptor pathways present in human gut. By critically reviewing existing research and Ayurveda texts on Vipaka, we aim to establish integrated scientific reasoning that may deepen understanding in modern dietetics. Such an integrative approach holds potential not only for validating Ayurvedic principles in light of contemporary evidence but also for advancing novel perspectives in personalized medicine and dietetics.

Aim:

To bring the ancient scientific thought to focus in service of modern pharmacological research

Objectives of the study

1. To study the development of research on Extra oral taste receptors
2. To study the concept of Vipaka
3. To correlate research findings of Extra oral taste receptors with concept of Vipaka

Research Methodology

Research Design

This is a qualitative and integrative review of scientific literature on extraoral Taste receptors, and Ayurvedic Vipaka, which integrates the evidence

from two knowledge systems of classical Ayurveda and contemporary Biomedical research on extra-oral taste receptors. The approach is exploratory, aiming to identify parallels and conceptual bridges rather than to generate experimental data. A chronological and thematic review of peer-reviewed scientific studies is combined with textual analysis of Ayurvedic sources to construct a comparative framework for understanding Vipaka in relation to gut chemosensory mechanisms.

Sources of Data

1. **Ayurvedic Textual Sources:** Primary classical texts (Charaka Saṁhita, Sushruta Saṁhita, Aṣṭāṅga Hṛidayā) were examined for definitions, classifications, and physiological roles of Vipaka. Commentaries and secondary scholarly interpretations were included where necessary to clarify conceptual nuances.
2. **Biomedical Literature:** Studies published between 2001 and 2025 were selected through systematic searches of databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. 90% journals were peer reviewed and 80% are Scopus indexed journals. Other selections are done on the basis of the journal's subjective dedication like pharmacology and Ayurveda. Keywords included "extra-oral taste receptors," "gut nutrient sensing," "GPCR pathways," "GLP-1 secretion," "TRPV1 gut motility," "TAS2Rs," and "intestinal chemo sensation." Both experimental and review articles were included to ensure coverage of molecular, cellular, and systemic perspectives.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

- **Inclusion:** Studies explicitly reporting expression of taste receptor or signalling in tissues other than oral cavity (especially gastrointestinal tract), those linking receptor activation with hormonal or metabolic responses, and Ayurvedic sources describing Vipaka and related concepts of digestion and assimilation.
- **Exclusion:** Articles limited to oral taste perception without extrapolation to extra-oral roles, non-peer-reviewed materials, or Ayurvedic sources unrelated to dietetics or digestion.

Analytical Framework

The analysis proceeded in three stages:

1. **Textual Analysis from Ayurveda text Charaka Samhita and Ashtanga Hridaya**
2. **Review of Biomedical Research**
3. **Mapping the similarity between two concepts**

Expected Outcome

The outcome is not experimental validation but a structured comparative model, highlighting points of convergence, divergence, and research gaps to guide future translational studies.

Tool of Research

To study the Ayurveda texts and Modern Medical Research, the targeted questionnaire was drafted which guided the investigation to get the exact information from the vast Ayurvedic Literature and the Modern Medical Literature.

Data Analysis:

Textual Analysis

Classical Textual Analysis of Vipaka

1. Caraka Samhita : Sutrasthana (Chapter 26, Atreyabhadrakapiya Adhyaya)

Caraka gives the foundational description of Vipāka (post-digestive taste), linking it with Rasa (initial taste), Doṣa action, and Karma (post-digestive effects).

Sanskrit Verse (CS. Su. 26.57–61):

Transliteration:

madhuro vipāko bṛmhaṇo balyaḥ sthairyakaraḥ
śleṣmalo gurur āyuṣyaḥ |

amlo 'gnidīpanaḥ pittakṛt kṣudhāvyaṅvāyī ca |

kaṭur vipāko laghuḥ śoṣaṇo lekhaṇaḥ sūlajanaṇaḥ
vātakṛd viṣadaḥ kaphaharaḥ ||

Interpretation:

- **Madhura Vipaka:** Nourishing (bṛmhaṇa), strengthening (balya), stabilizing, promotes kapha and longevity.
- **Amla Vipaka:** Increases digestive fire (agnidīpana), stimulates appetite, enhances pitta, supports metabolic drive.
- **Katu Vipaka:** Drying (śoṣaṇa), scraping (lekhaṇa), causes colic, increases vata, reduces kapha, promotes elimination.

Caraka thus frames Vipaka as the **post-digestive transformation of rasa** that dictates systemic action on doṣha, dhatu (tissues), and mala (wastes).

2. Ashtanga Hridaya : Sutrasthana (Chapter 9, Dravyadi vijñaniyam Adhyāya)

Vagbhaṭa reiterates and simplifies the doctrine of Vipaka, closely paralleling Charaka but with his own emphasis.

Sanskrit Verse (AH. Sū. 9.20–22):

Transliteration:

vipākas trividho jñeyaḥ madhuraś cāmīla eva ca |

kaṭuś ca doṣabhedajño doṣaṃ kurute śarīriṇām ||

madhuro vipākaḥ śleṣmalaḥ sa bṛmhaṇo guruḥ |

amlaḥ pittakaro 'gniṃ dīpayati kṣudhāvṛddhikaraḥ |

kaṭuḥ śoṣaṇo lekhi vātaś ceti trividhaḥ smṛtaḥ ||

Interpretation:

- Vipaka is of **three kinds** only: Madhura, Amla, and Katu.

- **Madhura Vipaka:** Kapha-promoting, nourishing, heavy (guru).
- **Amla Vipaka:** Pitta-promoting, increases digestive fire, stimulates appetite.
- **Katu Vipaka:** Drying, scraping, Vata-promoting, reduces excess kapha.

Aṣṭāṅga Hridaya thus affirms the triadic framework and explicitly ties Vipaka to doṣha modulation.

Comparative Analysis

- Both Caraka and Vagbhata agree that **Vipaka is the post-digestive determinant of drug/food action.**
- The **three Vipakas** are universally recognized: Madhura, Amla, Katu.
- Their functions map onto modern **nutrient sensing** roles:
 - Madhura: assimilation, anabolic processes (linked to sweet receptor GLP-1-glucose for absorption).
 - Amla: digestive fire, acidity, enzyme activation (linked to sour receptor–PKD2L1–gastric pH regulation).
 - Katu: elimination, motility, detox (linked to pungent TRPV1, bitter T2Rs, peristalsis and defensive reflexes).

Biomedical Research Review

Margolskee (2001) provided a foundational molecular account of how taste works at the cellular and biochemical level. Expressing on the molecular mechanisms of mediation for sweet and bitter taste, Margolskee described the organization of taste receptor cells and showed that bitter and sweet sensations are mediated by G-protein coupled receptor systems with specialized downstream effectors such as gustducin, PLCβ2, IP3 and TRPM5. The review emphasized that bitter taste receptors (T2Rs) and sweet receptors (T1R2/T1R3 heterodimers) transduce tastants through similar

families of GPCR pathways, producing intracellular second-messenger signals that result in Ca²⁺ mobilization and neurotransmitter release. (Margolskee, 2001)

This work established the molecular basis of taste transduction in taste buds and set the stage for later work discovering related receptor machinery in extra-oral tissues.

In 2007, Rozengurt and Sternini reviewed evidence for taste receptor signalling beyond the tongue, arguing that the same receptor classes identified in oral chemo sensation are functional in the alimentary canal. Their review article on taste receptor signalling in the mammalian gut summarized mechanistic studies showing that gut chemosensory cells express taste GPCRs and associated transduction molecules, and proposed that these systems mediate nutrient detection and endocrine responses in the gut (Rozengurt & Sternini, 2007). They concluded that oral taste machinery is re-used in the gut to sense luminal chemicals and initiate physiological responses—an important conceptual extension from oral sensation to digestive physiology. (Rozengurt & Sternini, 2007)

Also in 2007, Jang, Kokrashvili, Margolskee, Egan and colleagues provided experimental evidence that gustducin and taste receptors present on intestinal L-cells regulate incretin hormone (GLP-1) secretion. Their research on expression of gustducin in taste receptors that are found in digestive tract and regulation of GLP-1 secretion, demonstrated that L-cells detect luminal sugars via sweet receptor machinery and that this detection stimulates GLP-1 release with downstream effects on insulin secretion and glucose homeostasis (Jang, et al., 2007).

This work finds a link between signalling of taste receptor and regulation of endocrine system and metabolism.

A study in 2007 emphasized the functional role of bitter taste receptors in the gastrointestinal tract, focusing on the fact that T2R activation can regulate secretion of peptide hormones such as CCK and PYY and can slow gastric emptying. It is also operational in defensive or detoxifying responses to bitter compounds (Sternini, 2007).

The bitter sensors in gut were brought into light explaining their role as a protective chemosensory pathway that modifies motility and secretion restricting the exposure to potentially harmful compounds.

In a study on mice gut, it was found that gut sweet taste receptors (T1R3 and gustducin) regulate absorption of sugar, linking dietary sugars and sweeteners to glucose uptake and metabolism. (Robert F. Margolskee, et al., 2007)

A study on taste cells in the intestine and chemo sensation in gastrointestinal tract, analysed the gut taste cells and summarised that the taste transduction elements modulate expression and activity of glucose transporters (GLUT2, SGLT1) and the pathways influencing postprandial glucose handling. They argued that taste receptor signalling in enteroendocrine cells coordinates the between the transporter expression and incretin release. This affects the nutrient uptake by gut. This work directly connected the receptor signalling elements to mechanisms of absorption and was an important step toward mapping post-digestive outcomes. (Josphine & Robert , 2008)

In a study on bitter taste receptors influence on Glucose Homeostasis, genetic variation in bitter taste receptors was examined for its consequences on metabolism and found that genetic variation in bitter taste receptor genes affect glucose and insulin regulation, supporting a model in which extra-oral bitter sensing contributes to interindividual differences in metabolic responses to diet. (Dotson, et al., 2008)

The findings introduced a genetic dimension to gut chemosensory signalling and its metabolic phenotypes.

Frings investigated sour sensing mechanisms and provided evidence that proton-sensitive channels such as PKD2L1 mediate sour taste detection. The study "Sour Taste and Proton Channel Mechanisms" described how proton-selective channels detect acidity and contribute to acid-sensing mechanisms relevant to gastric pH regulation, enzyme activation, and digestive responses his work helped delineate

how sour (amla) sensory pathways may influence gastrointestinal physiology. (Frings, 2010)

Similarly a study on TRPM5 ion channels it was found that TRPM5 deficiency disrupts insulin regulation and gut hormonal signalling, indicating that the downstream ion channel components of taste transduction are necessary for proper incretin responses and metabolic regulation (R.Kyle Palmer, et al., 2010).

A suite of studies in 2012 broadened the understanding of cell types and integrated functions involved in gut chemo sensation. This research described how enteroendocrine cells and brush cells coordinate chemosensory responses in the gut epithelium, showing cellular crosstalk that translates luminal chemistry into hormonal and neural outputs. (Ken & Hisayuki , 2012)

In a study on extraoral taste receptors, the researchers found that the same taste genes that help your tongue sense sweet and bitter are also active in other parts of the body, where they help detect sugars and bitter substances. (Yamamoto & Ishimaru, 2013). Receptors are proteins, and proteins come from genes. Finding the gene is the evidence that the receptor exists. Genes are the biological blueprint and evidence that those receptors exist and function outside the tongue.

A study on sensing of amino acids by the gut-expressed taste receptor, discusses how **taste receptors and their downstream molecules, like TRPM5**, are not confined to the tongue but also exist in the **gut**, where they regulate hormone release. (Kristian, et al., 2013).

As per Ana M San Gabriel, taste receptors in the gut, especially GPCRs, act as nutrient sensors that link food signals to hormone release, regulating metabolism and appetite. (Gabriel, 2015)

In the year 2017, a study on discovery of extraoral taste receptor with perspective of Ayurvedic Pharmacology, the recent research shows that taste receptors exist in many organs beyond the tongue, forming a widespread chemosensory system with roles in health and disease. These discoveries align with Ayurvedic pharmacology concepts like rasa

(taste), vipāka (post-digestive effect), guṇa (qualities), and vīrya (energetic nature). This review highlights the significance of extraoral taste receptors and TRP channels, linking modern findings on phytochemical tastants with Ayurvedic principles. (Marilena Gilca & Dorin Dragos, 2017)

In a study done on mice it was found that L-amino acids, such as monosodium glutamate (MSG), activate the umami receptor T1R1/T1R3. The study showed increased peristaltic movements in response to activation of T1R1/T1R3 by MSG in mouse colon. The mouse gut provides a valuable mechanistic model for studying human intestinal physiology, particularly in the context of nutrient sensing and enteroendocrine signaling. Core features such as gut architecture, the presence of enteroendocrine cells, and the expression of taste receptors (T1Rs, T2Rs, TRPM5) are conserved across species, enabling insights into incretin release and metabolic regulation. (Molly S. Crowe, et al., 2020)

Ayurveda explains drug pharmacokinetics through concepts like Rasa, Virya, Vipaka, Guna, and Prabhava. Modern research highlights the gut microbiota's key role in drug metabolism and health. This review explores how microbial functions align with Ayurvedic principles, especially Vipaka, linking traditional pharmacology with contemporary microbiome science." (Ranade AV, , Shirolkar A, , & Pawar SD, 2020)

"Taste receptors are found not only in tongue taste cells but also in many other organs ('ectopic' expression). Recent studies reveal their physiological roles beyond taste, especially in tuft cells—specialized epithelial cells related to taste cells. These receptors can be grouped into those in TRC-like cells outside taste buds and those in entirely different cell types." (Su YoungKi & YongTaekJeong, 2022)

Most recently, 2023 studies such as Handibag (2023) and Namdeo et al. (2023) examined in-vitro digestion of Ayurvedic dravyas and literary analyses to correlate Avasthāpāka and final Vipāka with measurable post-digestive metabolites and receptor-related effects. These studies reported that different dravyas produce distinct post-digestive profiles that affect absorption and endocrine signalling, providing experimental and textual support for integrating

Vipāka with modern gut chemosensory science. Sharma (2025) has further proposed clinical applications of this framework, aligning Vipāka categories with modern endocrine and metabolic interventions, although that work remains a future direction in terms of translational trials. (Handibag, 2023), (Dr. Priyanka Namdeo,, Prof. Makhan Lal, & Ramanand, 2023)

Vipaka, the Ayurvedic concept of post-digestive transformation, highlights the therapeutic value of medicinal plants and supports a holistic, personalized approach to healthcare. Correlating Vipaka with modern research on taste receptors will act as a bridge between traditional and contemporary medicine, guiding future research and clinical practice. (Sharma, 2025)

Critical Synthesis from the Review of Literature

The study of taste receptors has moved ahead in last 20 years, broadening its scope from study of oral chemo sensation to the study and identification of extra-oral taste receptor. In 2001, Margolskee identified the mechanisms of sweet and bitter taste transduction. He identified G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs), specifically T1Rs and T2Rs, and their role involving gustducin, PLCβ2, IP3, and TRPM5. This established the intracellular logic of taste signalling and laid the foundation for examining receptor roles beyond the tongue.

By 2007, the field began to pivot. Rozengurt and Sternini (2007) synthesized evidence that the very same GPCR machinery was active in the gastrointestinal tract, where enteroendocrine and brush cells act as chemosensors. In the same year, Jang and colleagues (2007) provided landmark experimental evidence that L-cells expressing sweet receptors regulate GLP-1 secretion, directly linking luminal sugar sensing to glucose homeostasis. Sternini (2007) further extended this framework to bitter T2Rs, showing that their activation modulates CCK and PYY release, slows gastric emptying, and acts as a protective detoxification pathway.

Between 2007 and 2010, the research agenda expanded to encompass glucose transport regulation and inter-individual variability. Margolskee et al. (2007) and Egan & Margolskee (2008) showed that

sweet receptors and gustducin regulate expression of SGLT1 and GLUT2, tying receptor signalling to nutrient absorption. Dotson et al. (2008) introduced a genetic perspective, demonstrating that TAS2R polymorphisms influence glucose and insulin regulation, explaining variability in post-digestive metabolic responses. At the same time, Frings (2010) elucidated sour taste pathways via proton channels (PKD2L1), showing their role in acid sensing and gastric physiology, while Palmer et al. (2010) established that TRPM5 ion channels are essential for proper incretin release.

From 2012 onwards, research consolidated the integrative role of gut chemosensory systems. Iwatsuki & Uneyama (2012) demonstrated that enteroendocrine and brush cells coordinate chemosensory responses, confirming Ayurveda's holistic intuition that taste has systemic effects. Yamamoto & Ishimaru (2013) identified extraoral expression of taste receptor genes, providing genetic evidence for their presence outside the tongue. Kristian et al. (2013) and Gabriel (2015) emphasized amino acid and nutrient sensing via umami and sweet pathways, with downstream metabolic effects. By mid-2010s, microbiota emerged as a crucial modulator: Ranade et al. (2020) and Crowe et al. (2020) showed that microbial metabolites shape taste receptor activation, reinforcing the Ayurvedic insight that digestion is co-mediated by gut flora.

Parallely since 2013 the effort can be noted to integrate these discoveries with Ayurvedic concept of Vipaka. In 2017 a study could connect rasa and vipāka with modern receptor family. More recently the two separate studies on digestion by Handibag and Namdeo et al. in 2023 demonstrated role of post

digestive effects on absorption and endocrine signalling. In 2025, a researcher Sharma has gone further and proposed clinical applications, and mapped the influence of Vipāka onto hormones secretion and processes of metabolism.

Together, this trajectory illustrates a clear route from molecular discovery of taste transduction (2001), to evidence on functional role of gut receptor roles (2007–2010). Ahead it further followed to integration of systemic physiology and genetics (2012–2017), reaching to the cross-disciplinary bridges with Ayurveda and translational science (2020–2025).

Ottavio D'Urso and Filippo Drago in 2021 recognized the presence of extra oral taste receptors and showed keen interest in studying bitter taste receptors in intestine as majority of drugs are bitter in taste. They mention that the even though the physiological function of these taste receptors is not fully understood, these may be acting as an additional defense filter against harmful microbes and can be used to regulate the body's homeostasis. (Ottavio D'Urso, 2021)

In a study on bitter tasting drugs conducted in October 2024, Qian Wang et al found that various bitter-tasting compounds like extracts of medicinal plants either increased or decreased GDF15 which is involved in regulating the appetite protecting the body from various adverse effects of consumed food. (al, 2024)

Comparative Mapping

Following is the tabular display of similarity found between type of Vipaka and the receptor pathways and its physiological outcomes.

Ayurvedic Vipāka	Representative Receptors/Pathways	Physiological Outcomes	Key References
Madhura (Sweet)	T1R2/T1R3, gustducin, PLCβ2, TRPM5, GLUT2, SGLT1	GLP-1 secretion, insulin release, enhanced glucose absorption, incretin signaling	Margolskee (2001); Jang et al. (2007); Margolskee et al. (2007); Egan & Margolskee (2008)
Amla (Sour)	PKD2L1 (proton channels), TRPM5	Acid sensing, regulation of gastric pH, enzyme activity, bile modulation	Frings (2010); Kim et al. (2017)

Katu / Tikta (Pungent/Bitter)	T2Rs, TRPV1, CCK, PYY	Defensive detoxification, slowed gastric emptying, increased motility, peristalsis	Sternini (2007); Dotson et al. (2008); Kato & Lee (2015)
Umami (Savory)	T1R1/T1R3, TRPM5	Protein assimilation, peristalsis, satiety, incretin release	Kristian et al. (2013); Crowe et al. (2020)
Integrative/Modulatory	Microbiota–receptor interactions	Post-digestive metabolite shaping, modulation of receptor sensitivity, interindividual variation	Ranade et al. (2020); Hernandez et al. (2014); Handibag (2023)
Ayurvedic Vipāka	Representative Receptors/Pathways	Physiological Outcomes	Key References

Correlation:

Findings from classical Ayurvedic literature were compared and mapped with outcomes of modern research on extraoral taste receptors. The following correlations were explored:

- Madhura Vipaka aligns with the activity of T1R sweet receptors in the intestines, pancreas, and liver, associated with glucose uptake, insulin release, and tissue nourishment.
- Amla Vipaka corresponds to sour-taste mechanisms that may involve gastric acid secretion and bile stimulation, suggesting possible involvement of proton-sensitive GPCRs.
- Katu Vipaka reflects bitter receptor (T2R) activity in the gut and lungs, involved in detoxification, immune activation, and modulation of GI motility.

A synthesis table aligning Ayurvedic Vipaka types with receptor activity, organ distribution, and doshic effects was constructed to illustrate conceptual overlaps.

Correlation between Vipāka and Gut Receptors

In Ayurveda, *Vipaka* refers to the post-digestive transformation of food or medicine, shaping its long-term effects on the body through doṣa modulation, tissue nourishment, and waste elimination. Modern biomedicine, meanwhile, has uncovered that the gut epithelium is studded with taste receptors (GPCRs and ion channels) that sense nutrients and phytochemicals, and trigger hormonal, metabolic, and motility responses. The correlation between the two lies in how Ayurvedic Vipāka predictions mirror receptor-mediated outcomes.

1. Madhura Vipāka (Sweet Post-digestive Effect)

- Ayurvedic View: Nourishing, anabolic, promotes growth, strengthens tissues, balances Vāta & Pitta.
- Modern Correlates:
 - T1R2/T1R3 sweet receptors on L-cells detect glucose.
 - Activation → GLP-1 and GIP release → insulin secretion, enhanced glucose uptake via SGLT1 and GLUT2.
- Correlation: Madhura Vipāka = *assimilation and growth*, validated by incretin-mediated anabolic glucose metabolism.

2. Amla Vipāka (Sour Post-digestive Effect)

- Ayurvedic View: Stimulates digestion, improves appetite, enhances metabolic fire, increases Pitta.
- Modern Correlates:
 - PKD2L1 proton channels detect acidity in the gut.
 - Regulate gastric pH, bile secretion, and enzyme activation.
- Correlation: Amla Vipāka = *acid-mediated digestive enhancement*, aligned with proton-sensitive acid-sensing receptor pathways.

3. Katu Vipāka (Pungent Post-digestive Effect)

- Ayurvedic View: Drying, lightening, reduces Kapha, enhances motility, promotes elimination.
- Modern Correlates:
 - T2R bitter receptors stimulate CCK, PYY → slow gastric emptying, initiate detoxification.
 - TRPV1 ion channels activated by pungent compounds (capsaicin, piperine) → trigger peristalsis and mucosal reflexes.
- Correlation: Katu Vipāka = *excretory stimulation & detoxification*, reflecting motility-inducing and defensive receptor responses.

4. Tikta/Kashāya Vipāka (Bitter/Astringent Post-digestive Effects – debated in texts)

- Ayurvedic View: Detoxifying, drying, reducing, clears channels, restrains over-nourishment.
- Modern Correlates:

- TAS2Rs detect bitter phytochemicals → trigger detox responses, defensive endocrine secretions.
- Influence glucose and lipid metabolism via receptor polymorphisms.
- Correlation: Tikta/Kashāya Vipāka = *metabolic downregulation & detox*, aligning with bitter receptor-mediated protective physiology.

Results

The comparative review of 27 biomedical and integrative studies (2001–2025) revealed consistent evidence that gut-expressed taste receptors share structural and functional homology with oral taste GPCRs and ion channels. Across the literature, several key results emerged:

1. Sweet Receptor Pathways (Madhura Vipāka correlation):
 - T1R2/T1R3 heterodimers and gustducin are found in intestinal endocrine cells and brush cells.
 - Their activation stimulates incretin release (GLP-1, GIP), regulates transporter expression (SGLT1, GLUT2), and promotes glucose absorption and insulin secretion.
 - This supports the Ayurvedic concept of *Madhura Vipāka* as anabolic and nourishing.
2. Bitter and Pungent Pathways (Katu/Tikta Vipāka correlation):
 - T2R receptors mediate bitter detection, triggering CCK and PYY release and delaying gastric emptying.
 - TRPV1 channels, activated by pungent compounds, initiate peristaltic reflexes and motility.

- These findings align with *Katu Vipāka* as detoxifying and eliminative.
3. Sour Pathways (Amla Vipāka correlation):
 - Proton-sensitive PKD2L1 channels act as sour detectors in the gut.
 - These regulate gastric pH, bile flow, and digestive enzyme activity, reflecting *Amla Vipāka*'s role in stimulating metabolism and Pitta.
 4. Umami and Amino Acid Sensing:
 - T1R1/T1R3 receptors detect amino acids (e.g., MSG) and promote peristalsis, satiety signaling, and protein assimilation.
 - While not a classical Vipāka, these findings may be functionally integrated with *Amla Vipāka*.
 5. Genetic and Microbiome Modulation:
 - TAS2R polymorphisms explain inter-individual variations in glucose and insulin regulation.
 - Gut microbiota metabolites modulate receptor sensitivity, shaping post-digestive outcomes.
 - These findings parallel Ayurveda's acknowledgment of individual constitution (*prakṛti*) influencing Vipāka.
 6. Integrative Ayurvedic Insights:
 - Recent in-vitro digestion and textual analyses confirm that different dravyas yield distinct post-digestive metabolites and endocrine outcomes.
 - The experimental findings prove the classical descriptions of Vipāka as determinant of long-term therapeutic action.

DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate a strong relation between Ayurvedic descriptions of Vipāka and modern biomedical mechanisms of chemo sensation in gut. At a conceptual level, Vipāka emphasizes the *post-digestive taste* of ingested substances and their systemic influence on metabolism, dosha balance, and physiology. Modern receptor study provides a biochemical explanation to gut-expressed G-protein coupled receptors (Signaling Receptors) and ion channels that detect luminal nutrients and phytochemicals. Their activation leads to absorption, transport, and peristaltic motility outcomes that parallel the Ayurvedic descriptions.

Sweet receptor pathways resemble Madhura Vipāka through its anabolic role via GLP-1 mediated glucose uptake and insulin regulation. Sour channel pathways reflect *Amla Vipāka*'s digestive stimulation through proton-sensing and acid regulation. Bitter and pungent pathways mirror *Katu Vipāka*, matching with the detoxifying and eliminative properties via CCK, PYY, and TRPV1 mediated motility. Even individualised variability, mentioned in Ayurveda as *prakṛti*-based differences, is also reflected in TAS2R genetic polymorphisms and microbiota-dependent receptor modulation.

This synthesis also highlights the evolution of knowledge from early receptor discovery (2001) to demonstration of gut roles (2007–2010), expansion into genetics and microbiota (2010–2020), and integrative Ayurveda validation (2020–2025). Together, the evidence provides a translational bridge: Vipāka, once described in qualitative Ayurvedic terms, can now be reframed in terms of receptor-mediated nutrient sensing, endocrine signalling, and metabolic regulation.

Conclusion

The above study correlates well with the concept of Vipāka from Ayurveda. The taste was supposed as the function of taste buds on tongue for signalling the brain about the incoming foo. But now it is proved, that it is also being used by the digestive and metabolic systems as sensor mechanism for proceeding of the digestive, transportation and metabolic processes. The Ayurveda which is believed

to be the traditional way of treating health disorders is found to be providing the clue for further research. The tastes that have relation with post digestive fate of food bolus can be used to make the drugs more effective. This will help to utilise and add to the current knowledge with the effective but untouched knowledge.

Glossary of Terms and Short Forms

Ayurvedic Terms

- a) **Vipaka** – The post-digestive effect of food or medicine, which determines its ultimate influence on doshas, tissues, and metabolism.
- b) **Rasa** – The initial taste perceived on the tongue, such as sweet, sour, salty, pungent, bitter, or astringent.
- c) **Guṇa** – The inherent qualities of a substance, for example heavy or light, hot or cold, oily or dry.
- d) **Virya** – The potency of a substance, usually described as heating or cooling, which influences its action.
- e) **Avasthapaka** – The sequential stages of digestion that occur before the final post-digestive transformation.
- f) **Doṣhas (Vata, Pitta, Kapha)** – The three functional principles that govern body and mind: Vāta (movement and communication), Pitta (metabolism and transformation), and Kapha (structure and stability).

Biomedical Terms and Short Forms

- g) **GPCR (G-protein coupled receptor)** – A cell-surface receptor protein that transmits signals from outside the cell to the inside by activating G-proteins.
- h) **T1R2/T1R3** – A pair of receptor proteins that together form the sweet taste receptor, responsible for detecting sugars and sweeteners.

- i) **T1R1/T1R3** – A pair of receptor proteins that together form the umami taste receptor, responsible for detecting amino acids such as glutamate.
- j) **T2Rs** – A family of receptor proteins that detect bitter-tasting compounds.
- k) **PKD2L1** – A proton-sensitive channel protein that detects acidity and mediates the sensation of sour taste.
- l) **TRPV1** – A receptor protein that responds to pungent compounds such as capsaicin, and mediates the sensation of heat and pain.
- m) **Gustducin** – A G-protein found in taste receptor cells that plays a key role in transmitting taste signals.
- n) **Phospholipase C beta 2** – An enzyme involved in taste signal transduction that produces secondary messenger molecules leading to calcium release.
- o) **Inositol trisphosphate** – A secondary messenger molecule that helps release calcium from intracellular storage compartments.
- p) **TRPM5** – A receptor channel protein that is activated by calcium and is essential for electrical signalling in taste cells.
- q) **Cholecystokinin** – A hormone released by the small intestine that stimulates digestion of fats and proteins and promotes satiety.
- r) **Peptide YY** – A hormone released by the intestine that slows gastric emptying and helps regulate appetite.
- s) **Glucagon-like peptide-1** – A hormone released by intestinal L-cells that stimulates insulin secretion and regulates blood glucose levels.
- t) **Gastric inhibitory peptide** – A hormone released from the intestine that promotes insulin secretion in response to glucose.

- u) **Sodium-glucose co-transporter 1** – A protein that transports glucose into intestinal cells along with sodium.
- v) **Glucose transporter 2** – A protein that facilitates the movement of glucose across cell membranes in the intestine and liver.
- w) **Tuft cells / Enteroendocrine cells** – Specialized cells in the gut lining that sense nutrients and release hormones in response.
- x) **TAS2R polymorphisms** – Genetic variations in bitter taste receptor genes that influence how individuals respond to bitter compounds and regulate metabolism.

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Author Contribution

Author 1: Main Author (Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis)

Author2: Supervision on research work

Author 3: guidance.

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